

Decks Range Gola Village Community Begun District Buton District North

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Abstract: *Language means to give opponents meaningful speeches so that they can be understood and understood because in language, of course, requires excellent and correct linguistic tools. This study aims to analyze the deixis of the people of the village of Rante Gola, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency. This study uses a qualitative descriptive method carried out by not prioritizing the numbers, but prioritizes the depth of appreciation of the interaction between the concepts being studied independently. The population in this study was the community of Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency, the sample in this study amounted to 14 people. Data collection techniques in this study were recorded and recording techniques. Based on the approach used, the data analysis method used is the contextual method. The contextual way is a method of analysis that is applied to data by basing, calculating, and linking contexts. The results of the above research are deixis found in the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency, namely six types, namely: Deiksis People or Persona, place, time, discourse, social, and pointer.*

Catchphrases: *Deixis, Bonegunu, North Buton*

I. INTRODUCTION

Language in speech communities is used by the owners to collaborate in daily life, including in communication between students. The existence of language in human life is greatly influenced by the dynamics that occur or are experienced by the speech participants in the speech community concerned on the socio-cultural values that live and develop in determining the realization of the forms of language itself, including the use of deixis and politeness in acting.

Language shows a person's personal reflection. The character, character, or person of a person can be identified from the words he utters. The use of soft, polite, polite, systematic, orderly, clear, and straightforward language reflects the personality of the speaker. Conversely, through the use of language that is sarcasm, blasphemy, cursing, slandering, discrediting, provoking, mocking, or harassing, will image a person who is not virtuous.

Therefore, ineffective communication it is needed not only message clarity, but also politeness and politeness in language. Lakoff (2003). Deixis is the ability to distinguish precisely the nuances of meaning from the ideas to be conveyed and the ability to find forms that are suitable or appropriate to the situation and sense of value possessed by the listener community group.

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All utterances in acts of communication always contain three elements, namely (1) acts of locution in the form of speeches produced by a speaker, (2) acts of illocution in the way of intentions contained in utterances, and (3) does not need to be in the form of effects caused by statements. In line with this opinion, Searle (in Taufik: 2018) states that in one speech act at the same time there are three kinds of actions, namely (1) utterance in the form of words or sentences, (2) proportional acts in the way of references and predictions, and (3) illocutionary actions can be a statement, question, promise, order, and so on. The communicative effect is what sometimes has an impact on one's behavior.

Language can also be studied in terms of the meaning of the words (semantics) of each language spoken. The word semantics is a technical term that refers to the study of meaning. Semantics is said to be part of linguistics which sifts through communication. Semantics can be explained as a field that briefly studies the meaning of words and verses in language. The study of word meanings can be seen in terms of denotation and connotation meaning, meaning in context, the relationship of meaning to culture, changes in a sense, and forms of meaning rather than semantic relations. In terms of meaning in communication is one of the determining factors in politeness in language.

Not just speaking words but also doing something else, namely the speaker wants to convey specific purposes to the speech partner, for example, "I will put this here." Such speech acts are called deixis speech acts. Deixis that will be examined in this study is the use of deixis Kulisusu Dialect Community of Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency. The Kulisusu language of the Rante Gola Village Community is one of the native languages of Kulisusu, one of the original words of Muna. This is the fundamental reason for researchers to conduct research.

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Pragmatic

He terms pragmatics as we know it today was introduced by a philosopher named Charles Morris in 1938. When he discussed the general form of the science of sign (semiotic). He explained in Levinson, (in Risman: 2018) that semiotics has three fields of study, namely syntax (syntax), semantics (semantics), and pragmatics (pragmatic). Language is a linguistic study that examines the formal relationship between signs.

Semantics is a linguistic study of the sign's affiliation with the person who interprets the sign.

Since then, pragmatics has experienced two different meanings. On the one hand, pragmatics with the concept as intended by Morris above are still maintained. Here the term pragmatics is used in various book titles which discuss multiple problems such as psychopathology of communication and the evolution of symbol systems. On the other hand, the term pragmatics experiences a narrowing of meaning. In this case, a philosopher and logician named Carnap said that if in a study there is a particular reference to the speaker or in more general terms, the language user, then he determined that the research was in the field of pragmatic study.

Then in the subsequent development, by Levinson, (in risman: 2018) the notion is considered too narrow and exclusive; and therefore this understanding is modified into language studies that refer to or relate to factors and contextual aspects. In the previous description, it has been stated that pragmatics refers to the study of the use of language based on context. Fields of research relating to this matter which is then commonly known as pragmatic fields of study are deixis, presuppositions, speech acts, and conversational implications. Each area of study above is discussed in a manner.

Deixis

The word deiksis comes from the Greek word deiktikos which means "direct appointment." The term is used by Greek grammar in the sense of "pronoun pointer," which in Indonesian is the word "this" and "that."

Deixis was later introduced in the 20th century by Karl Buhler. A similar concept, broader in scope, was introduced by C.S Peirce, with the term indexicality. Peirce introduces the term indexical sign in English the primary form of the word (indexicality) is index, the meaning of which is something that points or shows or points.

According to Chaer (2010). Deixis is the relationship between words used in speech acts and referents of words that are not fixed or changeable. A word is said deixis if the referent or reference moves or changes depending on who is the speaker or depends on the time and place spoken. Another definition of deixis was put forward by Lyons (In Chaer, 2010) who explained that deixis is the location and identification of people, objects, events, processes or activities that are being discussed or that are being referred to in relation to the dimensions of space and time, when spoken by the speaker or the one spoken to.

Deixis is a word or phrase that refers to a word, phrase, or phrase that has been used or that will be given by Agustina, (2005). In the Big Indonesian Dictionary (2008), deixis is defined as a thing or function that points to something outside the language or pronominal pointing words. Deixis is words that have a changeable or sedentary referent. Setianingrum, (2003) Further about deixis, Leech (2003), deixis is a way to refer to specific nature using language that can only be interpreted according to the meaning assigned to by the speaker and influenced by the conversation situation.

Deixis can be interpreted as outside speech, where the center of the deixis orientation is always the speaker, which is not an element in the language itself, while anaphora refers to statement both referring to the words behind and referring to the words in front. (Setiawan, 2007). The deixis phenomenon is the most transparent way to describe the relationship between language and context in the structure of language itself. Words like me, here, now are deixis words whose meaning can be known if it is also known who, at what place, and when the words were said. So, the center of deixis orientation is the speaker.

From the explanation of the deixis above it can be concluded that deixis is a word, phrase or phrase whose references move depending on who is the speaker, the time and place of the language unit spoken.

Various types of deixis

Nababan 2007 explained that deixis was divided into six classes, namely deixis of people, place deixis, time deixis, discourse deixis, social deixis, and supporting deixis. Besides Kaswanti Purwo (Sumarsono, 2008) mentions several types of deixis, namely persona deixis, place, time, and pointer.

a. Deixis People of persona

The term persona comes from the Latin word persona as a translation of the Greek word prosopon, which means mask which also means the role or character that is performed by the showman. The term persona was chosen by linguists when it was caused by the similarity between language events and language games (Rogers, 2001). Personal deixis designates the role of the participant in the conversation event such as the speaker, the person being talked about, and other entities.

Deixis of people is determined according to the participant's role in the language event. The participant's position can be divided into three. The first is the first person, the category of the speaker's reference to himself or the group that involves him, for example me, us, and us. The second is the second person, the speaker reference category to a listener or more who is present with the first person, for example you, you, brother. The third is the third person, that is the reference category to the person who is not the speaker or hearer of the speech, whether present or not, for example he and them.

The first and second persona pronouns are exophoric. This means that the first and second references to the conversation situation (Purwo, 2004). Therefore, to find out who the speaker and the interlocutor we need to know the position of the speech time it is told Deiksis persona is the original deixis, while the deixis of time and place deixis is deixis of translation. In the opinion of Becker and Oka in Purwo (2004) that person deixis is the basis of orientation for the deixis of space and place and time.

b. Deixis Place

Place deixis is the giving of forms to locations according to participants in language events. All languages - including Indonesian - distinguish between "those who are close to the speaker" for example: here, and "those that are not close to the speaker." Nababan, (2007). For example the use of place deixis:

- a) Sit here.
- b) Gas LPG is sold here.

The phrase here in the first sentence refers to a tiny place, which is a chair or sofa. In the second sentence, the reference is broader; that is, a shop or other place of sale.

Example

deixis place in Indonesian that is far from the speaker:

"Bowo's house has been flooded. There are no inhabitants there."

c. Deixis Time

Deixis time is giving the form in the time as intended by speakers in the language event. In many languages, this time deixis is expressed in the "time" form. Nababan, (2007). For example yesterday, tomorrow, later, now, the day after tomorrow and others.

d. Deixis Discourse

Deixis discourse is a reference to certain parts of the discussion that have been given or are being developed. Nababan, (2007). Deixis discourse includes anaphora and katafora. Anaphora is the reappointment to something that was mentioned earlier in the speech with repetition or substitution. For example this, that and the previous one. Katara is the designation for something called later or what will be called. For example, the following, below, as follows, among other things, and between them.

Example of anaphora:

- a) "Uncle came from the village yesterday and brought his crops."
- b) "Because of its distinctive aroma, mangoes are widely bought."

From the two examples above, we can see that in the instance (a) it refers to the uncle mentioned earlier, while in illustration (b) it relates to the mango called later.

Example words:

- a) "The undersigned is"
- b) "Pragmatic types are as follows."
- c) "Which includes deixis, among others."

e. Social Deixis

Social deixis is a reference that is stated based on social differences that affect the role of the speaker and listener. That difference can be shown in the choice of words. In some languages, differences in the social level between the speaker and the listener are manifested in word selection and morphological systems of certain words. Nababan (2007). For

example, in situations of discussion between students and lecturers who are far different in their social status. Nababan (2007).

f. Deixis Pointer

In Indonesian, we refer to demonstrative or demonstrative pronouns "to refer to something close to the speaker, and that" to designate something far from the speaker. "Something" is not just objects or things but also circumstances, events, even time. Note the use in the following sentences.

- a) This problem must be resolved immediately.
- b) When the incident happened, I was a child.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Research Methods and Types

The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative research method. This method is considered suitable for language research. This research was conducted to analyze the dialysis of Kulisusu dialect on the people of Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency.

As well as the type of research. This type of research is a picture that fits the actual situation. Information gathering is done by direct questions and observations in the field, using standard observation tools.

Population and Sample

The community is the object of research. In a study population, in general, is a whole individual from certain aspects of language. Subroto (2002). The people in this study is the Community of Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency.

The sample in this study was all of the oral utterances of the community which contained meaning or purpose of the speech, in fact, the Indonesian language was recorded in 14 recorded sounds, which were recorded secretly without being known by the people studied. Because the total population studied was less than 100 people, the Research Sample took all societies to be sampled. So the sample in this study amounted to 14 people from the Rante Gola Village Community.

Data collection technique

Data collection techniques in this study are the recording technique and the note-taking technique. The recording technique is the acquisition of data by recording the use of spoken language that is spontaneous, while the recording technique is the acquisition of relevant data by logging data according to the aims and objectives of the study.

In addition to relying on recordings, researchers also use note-taking techniques as research tools. This note-taking technique is used to record the behavior patterns of the communication process between speakers and speech partners that occur in the community.

Record technique is intentionally used to avoid or prevent if the recording technique used unexpectedly is not recorded or deleted.

The use of both data collection techniques is done by researchers to make valid data. Either triangulation can make efforts to make the data genuinely compelling of data triangulation, source triangulation and triangulation of techniques or methods

Data analysis technique

Based on the approach used, the data analysis method used is the contextual method. Contextual methods are analytical methods applied to data by basing, calculating, and linking context. Before the data are analyzed using the contextual method, firstly the data concerning research regarding the use of speech acts by linking deixis to public courtesy. This study is intended so that this research activity can be objective to get the use of speech acts by linking deixis to the courtesy of the community. So that it can run scientifically or get accurate data.

IV. DISCUSSION

Research result

Deixis is the ability to distinguish precisely the nuances of meaning from the ideas to be conveyed and the ability to find forms that are suitable or appropriate to the situation and sense of value possessed by the listener community group.

In this study, more specifics concerning matters related to speech acts expressed by the public by looking at the rules of language dialect. So the language deixis described by the public by looking at the Kulisusu dialect of Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency.

Researchers look more at the conditions of the exclusion contained in the six existing as a form of pronunciation of the speech acts of the Kulisusu dialect, among them, the person or person deixis, place, time, discourse, social, and the pointer is there.

a. Deixis People or Persona

This research was conducted in two different situations, researchers conducted data searches based on deixis of people or persona in the Kulisusu dialect, Rante Gola village, Bonegunu sub-district, North Buton regency, firstly in the morning situation at 08.00, mothers wanted to shop at the Rantegola market and the second situation was a student who is still on vacation in the village. The quote deixis as follows:

Example

Respondent 1:

Ina, meanta tolako idaoano Rante Gola, ako tolako perongaronga

In the sentence above, shows Deixis People or Persona in the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 01 stated that the persona was excused because it confirmed the statement, or asked a mother that Mother, tomorrow we go to the market (Rantegola), then we will both go. So from dialect people or persona say as a form

of language used in an area or a community condition.

Example

Respondent 2:

hiina ina, meanta unskude kupojagaipo ana kaasi. Biasano miarahangku ilako isikolah, ako keimembali wakuu nsuere, kei jadi mimengertipo lae.

In the sentence above, it shows the person Deixis or Persona in the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 02 stated that the persona was excused because it confirmed the respondent's question 01 in answering his condition that No Mother, tomorrow I will look after my poor child. My husband used to go to school. I'll just go next time, just understand and. So from dialect people or persona say as a form of language used in a community condition.

Example

Respondent 3:

Tosepakatiomo, rouno ingkita betopentaa ai. Mentee duka nahina betobaawa. Ako topentaa okuda tolu wula iso, aisomo mentee ingkita hinaamo betosauri bumaawa.

In the sentence above, it shows Deixis People or Persona in the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 03 stated that the persona was excused because it confirmed the statement that Agrees, especially if we want this holiday, maybe we could meet again, the holiday was almost three months so it was rare we can meet again. So from dialect people or persona say as a form of language used in an area or a social class.

b. deixis place

This research was conducted on the situation of students who had been on vacation in Wantigola village. The researchers conducted a data search based on the location deixis at the Kulisusu dialect, Rante Gola village, Bonegunu sub-district, North Buton regency, in this situation they were discussing the length of time they did not meet and planned a meeting for friends. Her friend. The quote deixis as follows:

Example

Respondent 1:

Ingkoo ai hapai Kau molaa tou tokompulu-kompulu mbule lae.

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 01 states that the place has existed because it confirms the statement that this Ko why do we rarely gather e again. The word "gather" shows the place deixis, namely giving form to the location in the event of a language or a position to be gathered for.

Example

Respondent 2

Itahino membuku iokuda teyo vila rouno imokesa pemandanganno

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community,

that Respondent 02 stated that the place is existed because it confirms the statement that the beach is only close to the villa, because the view is very beautiful.

The word near the villa shows the place deixis, namely the giving of a form to a location in a language event or a location to be gathered for.

Example

Reponden 3:

Leumo tolako to aca-acara pekancunuika i empang round riasoa i mewalo ikano.

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 05 stated the existence of the place because it confirms the statement that let's go for grilling fish in the pond because the fish are delicious there. The word empang indicates place deixis, which is giving form to a location in a language event.

c. Deixis Time

This research was conducted on the situation of students who had been on vacation in Wantigola village. The researchers conducted a data search based on time deixis at the Kulisusu dialect, Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton District, in this situation they were discussing information on going to college. The quote deixis as follows:

Example

Resondent 1:

Memangno meanta ai tousu kumarajaa jam sahapa

In the sentence above, it shows deixis during the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 01 stated that the time was existed because it emphasized the statement that what time we will come to work tomorrow. The word clock refers to the deixis of time, namely the giving of forms over time as intended by the speaker in a language event.

Example

Repondent 2:

Dayimpia ingkita betolako idaoa round betopolo giu-giuno boninahu

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis during the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 02 stated that the time existed because it confirmed the statement that so when we go to the market to buy ingredients for cooking. The word when shows the time deixis, namely the giving of forms over time as intended by the speaker in a language event.

Example

Reponden 3:

Mentee oleono ahadi round i ompolemarasano te ingkita duka topentaa.

In the sentence above, it shows deixis during the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 03 stated that the time was existed because it emphasized the statement that later on Sunday only because many were selling, we happened to be off. The word Sunday

shows the time deixis, namely the giving of forms in the time span as intended by the speaker in a language event.

d. Deixis Discourse

This research was conducted to find data based on discourse deixis in Kulisusu dialect, Rante Gola village, Bonegunu sub-district, North Buton regency, discourse deixis is a reference to certain parts of the discourse that have been given or are being developed. Deixis discourse includes anaphora and katafora. The quote deixis as follows:

a) Anafora

The quotation in Anafora's discourse is as follows:

Example: 1

Pinolitamangku iteleu minai kampo inindua teduka ipowawa hasilino pombulaa

In the sentence above, shows the deixis of Anafora's discourse in the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Uncle came from the village yesterday to bring the results of Palawijaya. The sentence above shows the deixis of Anafora's discourse, namely the reappointment to something that was mentioned earlier in the speech with repetition or substitution.

Example: 2

Round woono imoiko, maka iopoo ayiko iomple ndo pooli

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of Anafora's discourse in the Kulisusu dialect of Rante Gola Village Community, that because of its distinctive aroma, many mangoes are bought. The sentence above shows the deixis of Anafora's discourse, namely the reappointment to something that was mentioned earlier in discussion with repetition or substitution.

Example: 3

Andingku kadipo keitelev minai kotano Bandung, round idade kadipo keyiari kuliano.

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of Anafora's discourse in the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that my brother had just returned from Bandung because he had just finished his studies there. The sentence above shows the deixis of Anafora's discourse, namely the reappointment to something that was mentioned earlier in the speech with repetition or substitution.

b) Katafora

The quotation in Anafora's discourse is as follows:

Example: 1

Ingkoo yoa'ayi tabeano boupowawa iyotongkat isikolah meanta jam 7 mewangu, te isee uterlambat

In the sentence above, it shows deixis Katafora discourse in the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that the following you must bring a stick at school, tomorrow at 7 am, and don't be late.

The sentence above shows the

deixis of Katafora's discourse that is the designation to something called later or which will be called.

Example: 2

Ipadaai ingkoo tabeano uweweuopo beitonia ako.

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of the word discourse in the Kulisusu dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that below you must correct it correctly. The sentence above shows the deixis of Katafora's discourse that is the designation to something called later or which will be called.

Example: 3

Yoa''ayai giu-giuno masaalah bo ginaunto akoaya.

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of Katafora discourse in the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that what is included in the types of problems will be as follows. The sentence above shows the deixis of Katafora's discourse that is the designation to something called later or which will be called.

e. Social Deixis

This research was conducted to find data based on social deixis at the Kulisusu dialect, Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency, there was a teacher and sword research that had a dialogue on community activities in Rantegola Village. The quote deixis as follows:

Example: 1

impia ingkita meto mulai rumapat ai?

In the sentence above, it shows the social deixis of the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 01 stated that it was time-consuming because it confirmed the statement that when we began the meeting. This sentence is said by a teacher to show social deixis, which is a reference stated based on social differences that affect the role of the speaker and listener. That difference can be shown in the choice of words. In some languages, differences in the social level between the speaker and the listener are manifested in word selection and / or morphological systems of certain words.

Example: 2

kengkaiko ingkita keto arimo kumompulu pak seharusnya tokumpulu saluwukita, ariako ingkita to mulai rapatno, kehina duka to sokoriindapo te wali-walihako duka mpriou, rouno dahopuluh ka olima menitno duka yorapatto.

In the sentence above, it shows the social deixis of the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 02 stated that the time was there because it emphasized the statement that if we have gathered the pack should all be collected first, then we will start the meeting, or wait for friends first, right? We're meeting in 15 minutes. This sentence is said by a trader to show social deixis, a reference stated based on social differences that affect the role of the speaker and listener. That difference can be shown in the

choice of words. In some languages, differences in the social level between the speaker and the listener are manifested in word selection and / or morphological systems of certain words.

Example: 3

i jadi, ingkita topesikori te wali-wali hako dahopuluh kaolima menitno, kehinna ndotele ingkita to mulaimo rumapat.

In the sentence above, it shows the social deixis of the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 03 stated that the time was justified because it confirmed the statement that it is possible, we will wait for friends in 15 minutes, if they do not come we will start the meeting. This sentence is said by a teacher to show social deixis, which is a reference stated based on social differences that affect the role of the speaker and listener. That difference can be shown in the choice of words. In some languages, differences in the social level between the speaker and the listener are manifested in word selection and morphological systems of certain words

f. Deixis Pointer

This research was conducted to find data based on Deixis pointers at the Kulisusu dialect, Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency, and there were studies of two teenagers who were discussing. The quote deixis as follows:

Example: 1

Tei ompole masaalau iko

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of the Rante Gola Village Community Dialect Indicator, that Respondent 01 stated that the pointer was being driven out because it confirms the statement that there are many of your problems. The word shows pointer deixis, which is a pointer pronoun "this" to designate something close to the speaker, and "that" to identify something far from the speaker. "Something" is not just objects or things but also circumstances, events, even time.

Example: 2

Isee u atu-aturu mia, marako ku didiuko kupompake helem yaai.

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of the Kulisusu Dialect of the Rante Gola Village Community, that Respondent 12 stated that the pointer was rejected because it affirmed the statement that Doesn't regulate people, later when you wear this helmet. This word shows the pointer deixis, the pronoun pointer "this" to designate something close to the speaker, and "that" to designate something far from the speaker. "Something" is not just objects or things but also circumstances, events, even time.

Example: 3

Iseepo mperiu u emosi ntaanu, memangno masaalau iko imomuna paselesaiano lede?

In the sentence above, it shows the deixis of the Rante Gola Village Community Dialect Indicator, that Respondent 03 states that the pointer is being driven out because it confirms the statement that Doesn't be emotional or not, is your problem quickly resolved? The word shows pointer deixis, which is a pointer pronoun "this" to designate something close to the speaker, and "that" to identify something far from the speaker. "Something" is not just objects or things but also circumstances, events, even time.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the above research, deixis found in the Kulisusu dialect of Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency, namely Annam types, namely: Deixis Persona or Persona, place, time, discourse, social issues, and bookmarks.

The suggestion of this research is that for the Rantegola community, it should be in conducting a language, it should always clarify every word that is spoken, so that the listener or communicator can provide Pigbeg or reciprocity of what we say and for the academics to give a more significant understanding of the Use Speech Deiksis Kulisusu Dialect Community of Rante Gola Village, Bonegunu District, North Buton Regency.

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